

Some Triaryltin Acetates

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Tri-*o*-tolyltin acetate, tri-*p*-tolyltin acetate, and tribenzyltin acetate have been prepared in good yields by the interaction of silver acetate with corresponding triaryltin iodide in an inert solvent. The compounds have been characterised and their infrared spectra show characteristic frequencies which have been assigned to the various modes of vibration associated with co-valent acetates. The structure of the compounds on the basis of the separation between the asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of the -COO group has been discussed. It is concluded that in contrast to triphenyl and some trialkyltin acetates which possess a linear polymeric structure having penta co-ordinated tin atom in the solid state, the three acetates examined in this work possess monomolecular ester type structure with tetra co-valent tin atom.

Vander Kerk and Luijten to whom many of the new developments in the field of organotin chemistry are due, were the first to describe the preparation of a number of trialkyltin¹ and triaryltin² acetates. Trialkyltin acetates have been subjected to exhaustive structural studies. Thus Freeman³ reported tributyltin acetate to be ionic and Okawara et al⁴ suggested a similar structure for methyltin acetates. Recent studies^{5,6} have, however, shown that in the solid state trimethyltin acetate has a tin atom weakly co-ordinated by the two oxygen atoms, forming a linear chain in which the planar C₃Sn group is bridged by the -OCO-unit having a C_{2v} symmetry. This weak bridging in the acetate is destroyed in a non-polar solvent to give a monomeric trialkyltin carboxylate possessing an ester type carboxyl group.

Triphenyltin acetate was prepared for the first time by Luijten and Vander Kerk¹ by the interaction of triphenyltin hydroxide with glacial acetic acid. In a later communication² they undertook comparative antifungal studies of a number of triaryltin acetates. Srivastava and Tandon⁷ found that anhydrous silver acetate converts triphenyltin iodide in boiling benzene into corresponding organotin acetate.

The present investigation describes the preparation of the three acetates viz., tri *o*-tolyltin, tri *p*-tolyltin and tribenzyltin acetates by "silver salt conversion" method⁸ and discusses their structure on the basis of the observed infra-red

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absorption frequencies. Tri *o*-tolyltin acetate is a new compound and Luijten and Vander Kerk² failed to obtain it by the interaction of bis tri *o*-tolyltin oxide with glacial acetic acid. Tri *p*-tolyltin acetate has now been obtained in almost three times the yield of that reported previously².

EXPERIMENTAL

Triaryltin iodides used as starting materials in these preparations were synthesised as described in our previous communication¹.

The three triorganotin acetates were prepared as follows :

To 5 g. of dry freshly prepared silver acetate in 20 ml. of boiling benzene was added a solution of 3 g. of triaryltin iodide in 15 ml. of benzene. After refluxing the mixture for 10-15 minutes the insoluble silver salts were filtered off. The filtrate on removal of the solvent gave white solid triaryltin acetate, which was then recrystallised from petroleum ether.

The three triaryltin acetates are well defined stable solids, soluble in common organic solvents (benzene, ether, chloroform etc.). Table I lists the experimental results for the three organotin compounds.

TABLE I

Experimental Results for Triaryltin Acetates

	Tri <i>o</i> -tolyltin acetate.	Tri <i>p</i> -tolyltin acetate.	Tribenzyltin acetate.	Calcd. for C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₂ Sn.
M.P.	95°	113°	119°	
Yields.	57%	68%	71%	
Cryst. solvent.	Pet-ether (60-80°)	Pet-ether (40-60°)	Pet-ether (40-60°)	
Mol. Wt. Cryoscopic in benzene	429	437	432	450
<i>Analysis</i>				
C%	60.8	61.0	61.1	61.3
H%	4.9	4.9	5.0	5.3
Sn%	25.9	26.5	26.1	26.2

Infrared Spectra : The infrared spectra of the three triaryltin acetates were recorded in the range 4000–700 cm⁻¹ using a Perkin Elmer infra-ray cord. The samples for measurement were prepared in potassium bromide disc and also in carbon tetrachloride solution. No significant difference in the absorption bands was observed in the two media employed for making samples. The characteristic absorption bands associated with the acetate group in these compounds in solid potassium bromide discs are listed in table II. The corresponding frequencies

reported for triphenyl and some trialkyltin acetates have also been included in the table for purpose of comparison.

TABLE II

Characteristic absorption frequencies of acetate group in $R_3S_NOOC.CH_3$

R =	Asym-COO str. (cm^{-1})	Sym. -COO str. (cm^{-1})	Separation between 2 and 3	C-C str. (cm^{-1})	-COO scissor (cm^{-1})	Reference
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
<i>o</i> -tolyl	1653s	1298 m	355	928 w	692 m	This work
<i>p</i> -tolyl	1639s	1302 s	337	934 m	699 s	This work
benzyl	1618s	1319 m	299	913 w	695 m	This work
Alkyl (Solid)	1570 ± 6	1418 ± 10	~ 150	940 w	664 s	4 and 6
Alkyl (Dissolved)	1649 ± 6	1302 ± 2	~ 350	—	—	6
Phenyl (Solid)	1524v s	1422 s	102	936 w	—	10 and 11
	1530	1425	105			
Phenyl (Dissolved)	1639v.s	1311 s	308	934 w	—	10

s=strong, m=medium, w=weak v=very.

The strong absorption associated with the asymmetric stretching of C=O at $1750-1725cm^{-1}$, identified by Srivastava and Onyszchuk¹² for tertiary butyl acetate $(CH_3)_3COOCCH_3$ and trimethylacetoxysterane $(CH_3)_3GeOOCCH_3$ and by Freeman⁵ in the case of trimethylacetoxysilane $(CH_3)_3SiOOCCH_3$ is absent in triaryltin and trialkyltin acetates. Okawara et al⁴ and Janssen et al⁶ studied the infrared spectra of a number of trialkyltin acetates and found strong absorptions at $1570 \pm 6cm^{-1}$ and $1418 \pm 10cm^{-1}$, which they assigned to the asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of -COO group respectively. On comparison of these absorptions with the corresponding bands of sodium acetate¹³ at $1582 cm^{-1}$ and $1425 cm^{-1}$ for asymmetric and symmetric vibrations respectively, Okawara et al⁴ concluded that the trialkyltin acetates are essentially ionic and the spectra are interpreted as superpositions of the absorptions of the acetate anion and trialkyltin cations. However, it has been pointed out by Beattie and Gilson⁵ and also by Janssen et al⁶ that these similarities do not unequivocally point to an ionic structure but can be explained due to the presence of the bridging acetate group between the two trialkyltin moieties, giving a linear polymeric structure having a penta co-ordinated tin atom as shown below,

10. S. K. Tandon, Ph. D. Thesis, Lucknow University, Lucknow.

11. R. C. Poller, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1962, **24**, 598.

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The extent of separation between asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of the -COO group has been utilised in the past as a means of distinguishing between linear polymeric and monomolecular trialkyltin carboxylates^{14,6}. It is evident from the data collected in column 4 of the table II that -COO bands of trialkyl and triphenyltin acetates in the solid state are similar to those observed for salt like carboxylate groups (sodium acetate, separation=157 cm⁻¹)¹⁸. Upon dissolution in carbon tetrachloride, a non polar solvent, the magnitude of the separation between the two -COO stretching vibrations move more than half way towards the normal positions for organic esters (separation 500 cm⁻¹)¹⁵. This has been explained on the basis, that weak bridging in some solid organotin acetates (Structure-I), is destroyed in non-polar solvents to give monomeric acetates possessing an ester type carboxyl group (Structure II).

(Structure-II)

It has been pointed out earlier that the absorption frequencies of asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of the -COO group in triaryltin acetates examined in this work do not undergo a change when examined in the solid state in potassium bromide disc or in 1% solution of carbon tetrachloride. An examination of the data shows that the separation between the two -COO stretching frequencies listed in column 4 of table-II are close to ester type compounds. Since the compounds possess relatively low melting points, are soluble in common organic solvents and cryoscopic measurements in benzene show them to be monomeric, they are assigned structure-II, in which the central tin atom is tetra-covalent.

A linear polymeric structure having penta co-ordinated tin for these compounds is less likely because of the steric hindrance offered by relatively bulky tolyl and benzyl groups. Janssen et al⁶ observed that lengthening of the alkyl group on either the metal or the carboxylate group in trialkyltin carboxylates results in destabilisation of structure-I by steric effects. In this connection reference may also be made to the observations of Srivastava and Onyszchuk¹² for tertiarybutyl and trimethylgermyl acetates which show no change in the -COO stretching frequencies when examined in solution or solid phases indicating tetra co-valency for germanium atom.

14. H. Sato and R. Okawara, "International symposium on molecular structure and spectroscopy", Tokyo, Japan, 1962.
15. L. J. Bellamy, "The infrared spectra of complex molecules", Johns Wiley and Sons; New York (1958).

The two other bands associated with the acetate group, C-C stretching and -COO scissor observed in the present work for the three triaryltin acetates are in close proximity to those identified by Okawara et al in trimethyltin acetates⁴. These bands are thus not much dependent on as to whether, the acetate group is acting as a bidentate or as an unidentate. In the spectra of the ortho and *p*-tolyltin acetates, other absorption bands (not listed in the table) correspond to the disubstituted benzene derivatives of tin¹⁶ and in the case of the corresponding benzyl compound are similar to those in tribenzyltin chloride reported by Griffith and Derwish¹⁷.

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